

Reassessment of the distribution area and conservation status of *Xeroplexa setubalensis* (Pfeiffer, 1850), an endemic Portuguese land snail

Evaluación del área de distribución y del estado de conservación de *Xeroplexa setubalensis* (Pfeiffer, 1850), un caracol terrestre portugués

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ABSTRACT

In this paper we present the distribution area of *Xeroplexa setubalensis*, a land snail endemic to the Serra da Arrábida and littoral cliffs in the Setúbal peninsula, Portugal, based on specific fieldwork and compiled sporadic information. Its distribution area is extended ≈20 km westwards of previously known locations, along a narrow strip associated with limestone facing southwards. With the data obtained we reassessed the IUCN conservation status as endangered EN, based on a severely fragmented extent of occurrence, reduced area of occupancy with inferred continuing decline.

RESUMEN

En este artículo presentamos el área de distribución de *Xeroplexa setubalensis*, un caracol terrestre endémico de Serra da Arrábida y los acantilados costeros de la península de Setúbal, Portugal, basado en trabajo de campo específico e información recopilada esporádica. Su área de distribución se extiende ≈20 km al oeste de sitios previamente conocidos, a lo largo de una estrecha franja asociada con calizas orientadas al sur. Con los datos obtenidos, reevaluamos el status de conservación de la UICN como EN “en peligro de extinción”, en función de una extensión de ocurrencia severamente fragmentada, área de ocupación reducida con una disminución continua inferida.

RESUMO

Neste artigo apresentamos a área de distribuição de *Xeroplexa setubalensis*, um caracol terrestre endémico da Serra da Arrábida e das falésias litorais da península de Setúbal,

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Portugal, com base em trabalho de campo específico e informação esporádica compilada. A sua área de distribuição estende-se ≈20 km para oeste dos locais anteriormente conhecidos, ao longo de uma faixa estreita associada a calcários virados a sul. Com os dados obtidos reavaliámos o estatuto de conservação da IUCN como “em perigo” EN, com base numa extensão de ocorrência severamente fragmentada, área de ocupação reduzida com declínio contínuo inferido.

KEY WORDS: landsnails, endemic, consevation, *Xeroplexa setubalensis*, Geomitridae, IUCN conservation status. PALABRAS CLAVE: caracoles terrestres, endémico, conservación, *Xeroplexa setubalensis*, Geomitridae, IUCN estatus de conservación.

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INTRODUCTION

The land snail *Xeroplexa setubalensis* (Gastropoda: Geomitridae) (Figure 1) was initially described by Arthur MORELET (1845: 61-62) as *Helix serrula*, as inhabiting “the rocky hills that rise north of Setúbal, on the seaside”. Nevertheless, the name *Helix serrula* Morelet, 1845 was preoccupied by *Helix serrula* Benson, 1836. Louis PFEIFFER (1850) proposed the name *Helix setubalensis*, and indicates its occurrence in “Lusitania”, near Setúbal.

Augusto NOBRE (1941: 98-99) indicated occurrences of this species in Outão and frequently on the cliffs of Arrábida Mountains, especially near the castle of São Filipe, close to the walls of the old fortress, fixed to the stems of grasses or under stones and on the walls.

Edmund GITTEBERGER (1985) placed the species under the generic name *Candidula* Kobelt, 1871. This name will remain unchanged until the molecular study by CHUECA ET AL. (2018) where almost all *Candidula* species in Portugal are attributed to the genus *Xeroplexa* Monterosato, 1892 (with the exception of *Candidula codia* (Bourguignat, 1860)), where *Xeroplexa setubalensis* is the type species by subsequent designation (KOBELT, 1892).

The distinctive sharply keeled and serrated shell can only be compared to another congeneric species, *Xeroplexa coudensis* (HOLYOAK & HOLYOAK, 2010), which can be found about 150 km north (HOLYOAK & HOLYOAK, 2010; MOREIRA,

CALADO & DIAS, 2015). Still, as noted by HOLYOAK & HOLYOAK (2014), both species differ markedly in body colour: whereas *X. setubalensis* is very pale, *X. coudensis* has a blackish body, and length of penial flagellum: shorter than epiphallus in *X. setubalensis* (ca. 0.5–0.7×) and longer (ca. 1.5×) in *X. coudensis*.

The distribution of *Xeroplexa setubalensis* distribution was considered restricted to Serra da Arrábida (between Sesimbra and Setúbal), but HOLYOAK & HOLYOAK (2014) added some locations west of Sesimbra, near Cape Espichel. This Portuguese endemic species is listed as “Endangered” at the IUCN Red List (MARTÍNEZ-ORTÍ, 2011), given its restricted extent of occurrence (EOO = 100 km²) and area of occupancy (AOO = 10 km²) in just one location at Serra da Arrábida. A decline in the quality and extent of the habitat due to fires, road construction and tourism was considered the main threat to this species. Furthermore, it was assumed that the population of this species could have been heavily affected by a fire spread across significant parts of its distribution area, in 2004. Therefore, it is assessed as Endangered (EN) B1ab(iii) + 2ab(iii). The same assessment emphasizes the need for more research on the population size, the distribution and the effects of human disturbances and rural fires (MARTÍNEZ-ORTÍ, 2011). Although not in the scope of their work, HOLYOAK & HOLYOAK (2014)

Figure 1. Live specimen of *Xeroplexa setubalensis*. Shell diameter: 11 mm. Photo by Gonçalo Rosa.
Figura 1. Exemplar vivo de Xeroplexa setubalensis. Diâmetro da concha: 11 mm. Foto de Gonçalo Rosa.

consider that the conservation status “should probably be revised to “Vulnerable”, pending detailed surveys”.

In this paper we update the distribution range of this endemic land snail, based on new surveys and compiled data, and reassess the conservation status of the species category by applying IUCN criteria.

METHODS

Study area

Based on historical data and recent work (see introduction),- a target survey area of about 22800ha (38°28'N; 8° 58'W) was established, encompassing the known distribution range, but extending it to adjacent regions. The whole region is included in a Natura 2000 Site (the Arrábida Espichel – PTCON0010) and mostly in the Arrábida Natural Park (Figure 2).

FONSECA, ZÉZERE & NEVES (2014) characterize the Serra da Arrábida (501 meters above m.s.m.) as “a small WSW-ENE trending Alpine orogenic belt of

Miocene age, characterized by south verging folds and thrust planes connected to sinistral NNE-SSW and N-S strike-slip faults”. An almost complete sedimentary sequence from lower Jurassic (compact limestone, dolomites on the cliffs to the sea level) to Pliocene is exposed. Therefore, Serra da Arrábida is mainly established in limestone formations (compact limestones to marls and sandstones) where abandoned and active quarries testify its use since a long time (MANUPPELLA *ET AL.*, 1999). The Mediterranean red soils (GOMES PEDRO, 1991) derived from dolomitic limestone, determine a vegetation of great richness and originality (COSTA *ET AL.*, 2005). In Serra da Arrábida, vegetation can assume a multiple number of variations, depending on local conditions and human land use history (CATARINO, CORREIA & CORREIA 1982; MEIRA-NETO *ET AL.*, 2011). It varies from shrubland to woodland and comprises more than 1450 botanical species (GOMES PEDRO, 1998; RASTEIRO, 2019), with several rare endemisms (e.g., *Convolvulus fernandesii* P. Silva & Teles,

Figure 2. Study area included in the Setúbal Peninsula, mainland Portugal (left) and detailed information (right) on 2×2 km tetrads used to sample the land snail *Xeroplexa setubalensis*. Dark grid squares indicate presence, either living individuals or shells. Small white squares correspond to location of 5×5 m quadrats used to assess population density. The type-locality where the species was described is located at the eastern limit of the grid

Figura 2. Área de estudio incluida en la península de Setúbal, Portugal continental (izquierda) e información detallada (derecha) sobre tétradas de 2×2 km utilizadas para muestrear el caracol terrestre *Xeroplexa setubalensis*. Los cuadrados oscuros indican presencia, ya sea de individuos vivos o de conchas. Los pequeños cuadrados blancos corresponden a la ubicación de los cuadrantes de 5×5 m utilizados para evaluar la densidad de población. La localidad tipo donde se describió la especie se encuentra en el límite oriental de la cuadrícula.

1980 and *Euphorbia pedroi* Molero & Rovira, 1997) occurring only in dry rocky slopes facing the sea (COSTA ET AL., 2005) between Sesimbra and Espichel.

Geographical distribution, geological formations and habitat use

In addition to gathering published (i.e., MARTÍNEZ-ORTÍ, 2011; HOLYOAK & HOLYOAK, 2014), and our unpublished information on recent occurrences of the species (2009-2022), we surveyed the region using the methodology defined in MOREIRA ET AL. (2015). We set a grid of fifty-seven 2 km^2 tetrads (each of which comprise four 1 km^2 grid cells) totalling 228 km^2 . The surveys were carried out from 2015 to 2018. Each tetrad was inspected for about 15-30

minutes, depending on vegetation density, by a group of 10-15 volunteers (Lusófona University students and teachers from the Biology BSc), searching suitable micro-habitats in each location. The presence or absence of live specimens and empty shells was recorded, and the respective detailed spot was registered with a GPS and latter incorporated into a Geographic Information System.

The land cover type and geologic strata where the species was found, were determined by overlaying occurrence locations with CORINE LAND COVER maps (2018) (BÜTTNER & KOSZTRA, 2017) and geological map (MANUPPELLA ET AL., 1999) in the GIS.

Population estimates

Based on the previous task, 12 quadrats 25m² each (5×5m) were spread in two of the tetrads where live animals were known to occur in apparently suitable habitat adjacent to road and tracks (Figure 2). Minimum distance between quadrats ranged between 30 to 180 m. These quadrats were visited by groups of four people, with all live snails and shells within the quadrat being recorded. Density estimates were obtained by dividing the number of individual snails by the quadrat area, thus not adjusted for detectability. Given the small sample size, and other methodological limitations (no detectability corrections, snapshot census etc.), the mean density (and respective S.E) found are considered a crude over estimation as it is not expected that similar conditions and suitable habitat occurred through the distribution area.

Assessing the conservation status

We conducted an evaluation of the conservation status of *Xeroplexa setubalensis* by applying the IUCN criteria (IUCN, 2012). These criteria have been specifically designed to offer a clear and objective framework for categorizing species based on their risk of extinction. The IUCN classification system relies on five distinct criteria:

- A—Population reduction
- B—Geographic range
- C—Small population size and decline
- D—Very small or restricted population
- E—Quantitative analysis of extinction risk

To assess the conservation status of the species, we employed the IUCN criteria, and we listed those that qualified the species for the highest category. The extent of occurrence (EOO) was determined using a minimum convex polygon, which is the smallest polygon containing all occurrence sites and where no internal angle exceeds 180 degrees. We exclude areas of obviously unsuitable habitat (i.e., continuous urban fabric, active mineral extraction sites).

This measurement was conducted separately for the entire dataset, which includes both live animals and empty shells, as well as using only the locations of live specimens. The area of occupancy (AOO) was identified as the portion of the extent of occurrence that is actually inhabited by the species. Within the AOO, we further identify possible discontinuities due to evident habitat fragmentation (IUCN, 2012). In order to evaluate the potential threats to the species, we utilized the IUCN Threats Classification Scheme (IUCN, 2012).

RESULTS

Geographic distribution pattern

We detected the presence of the species (mainly by empty shells) in 33% of the surveyed tetrads and documented a total of 43 different spots where the species was present. The extent of occurrence (EOO) of the species, considering both live specimens and empty shell remains, was found to be 41 square kilometers. However, when considering only live animals, the EOO was smaller, specifically 16 square kilometers. Contrary to what happened in a previous study on a sister species, where searching for snails was relatively easy (MOREIRA ET AL., 2015), search for this species in certain locations turned out to be extremely difficult, especially when a dense woodland cover of *Quercus coccifera* and associated shrubland species occurred. In these cases, prospection was almost always restricted to roadsides or open land with sparse vegetation. Once detected the presence of snails, these vegetation types were included in the Area of Occupancy (AOO). Nevertheless, the obtained AOO was smaller (5.3 km² for live snails and 9.9 km² for both live and shell remains) than EOO, because individuals appeared to be concentrated in a narrow strip of cliffs facing southwards (max ≈1 km width), following the geological and vegetation strata where snails were found. AOO was also considered fragmented in three (two, if we consider the distribution of live individuals only)

Figure 3. Occurrences of *Xeroplexa setubalensis*. Location of living *Xeroplexa setubalensis* (white dots) and empty shells (black dots), within the inferred Area of occupancy AOO, respectively for the whole data set (light grey) and alive specimens (strip pattern). Areas where the population seems to be fragmented, either by urban settlements (e.g., Sesimbra village) or by active quarries (e.g., SECIL) are indicated as (?).

Figura 3. Ocurrencias de *Xeroplexa setubalensis*. Ubicación de *Xeroplexa setubalensis* viva (puntos blancos) y conchas vacías (puntos negros), dentro del Área de ocupación AOO inferida, respectivamente para todo el conjunto de datos (gris claro) y especímenes vivos (patrón de líneas). Se indican por (?) las áreas donde la población parece estar fragmentada, ya sea por asentamientos urbanos (por ejemplo, el pueblo de Sesimbra) o por canteras activas (por ejemplo, SECIL).

main locations with two discontinuities mainly due to active quarries and imperious urban areas (Figure 3).

Geology and habitat use

Using CORINE land cover categories, the species was mostly found on heathlands with open herbaceous grasses and sclerophyllous (scrub) vegetation. The occurrence of snails was also detected in sparsely vegetated rock formations facing the sea. Live animals were most frequently found underneath limestone boulders or in crevices, except on one occasion when it was raining and snails were found crawling on the exposed surface of the rock. Occasionally, live specimens were also found attached to herbaceous vegetation, a situation very similar to that found for *Xeroplexa coudensis* (MOREIRA ET AL., 2015). Some live specimens were found under dumped construction debris, in an

inoperative quarry, near Sesimbra. The species has not been detected either in agriculture or in forest patches. Altitude at registered sites ranged between ≈ 10 m a.s.l. to ≈ 210 m a.s.l. According to our data, the distribution of *X. setubalensis* stands almost exclusively on a narrow strip of compact limestones and dolomites from the Lower-Middle Jurassic which correspond to 23% of the geological formations of the surveyed area. Only the easternmost two locations are on sandy-limestone from the upper Jurassic. In fact, ca. 37% of the snail detection was in quarry limestones and 14% on dolomites, which only represents respectively 7% and 3.5% of the total surveyed area.

Population estimates

All the 12 sampled 25m² quadrats yielded empty shells of *X. setubalensis*, although live individuals were found

only in 6 samples. Where detected, the number of live snails varied between 2 and 6 and was correlated with the number of empty shells found in the quadrat ($r=0.755$, $p<0.05$, $n=12$). The average density (\pm standard error) of live snails in the sampled quadrats was $0.067\pm 0.023/\text{m}^2$. Extrapolation of this density to an area of 5.3 km^2 yielded a population estimate of 230.011- 476.655 individuals. This interval should be considered overestimated, given that no detectability corrections were made and the quadrats were implemented across areas where *X. setubalensis* had been previously detected.

Potential threats to the species

According to the IUCN threat classification scheme (version 3.2), we identified the primary potential threat to the population as follows:

Quarrying: Despite being a natural park, there are still some quarries in operation in the region, where limestone is mined for stone and gravel extraction. The consequences of this impact encompass not only the direct destruction of habitat and the loss of some individuals but also the potential harm caused by dust generated during excavation. One quarry in particular ($38^{\circ}26'52.5''\text{N}$ $9^{\circ}03'47.0''\text{W}$), property of the company Sobrissul, represents a direct threat to the integrity of the distribution area of the species, as its southern limits are only 80 meters from the sea and the cliff is unstable. Prospections of the snail north of the quarry were unfruitful, resulting in a bottleneck on the distribution area. Fortunately, a previous project to open the quarry to the sea was abandoned. Besides this, Arrábida Natural Park also includes a cement factory, property of the company Secil with two contiguous quarries in the eastside of the distribution area, near the presumable type-locality of the species. Expansion of the quarries is in the plans of the cement company, with a recent request to explore 18.5 ha of a pristine area, that is included in the polygon of the distribution area (EOO) of the species. The request was not authorized by the Por-

tuguese environmental authorities, alleging unconformity with current legislation (CCDR-LVT, 2023). Still, the threat is real as the cement factory is running out of raw materials to keep operating. This impact is therefore assessed as having a high level of significance.

Wildfires: Wildfires constitute a risk factor which may significantly impact a substantial portion of the species' distribution range in a single event, as pointed out in IUCN previous species assessment (MARTINEZ-ORTÍ, 2011). Wildfires can directly harm snails through incineration, dehydration, and contamination from pollutants released during organic material combustion. However, the relative importance of each of these factors remains uncertain. Additionally, wildfires can adversely affect the quality of the snail's habitat (NICOLAI & ANSART, 2017). It is important to note that wildfires primarily occur during the dry season when individual snails often aestivate in concealed locations, like crevices. The depth of these hiding places may provide some protection during wildfires, especially in habitats dominated by boulders and rock outcrops. Therefore, the impact of wildfires on this species may not be as significant as previously described, and this topic would justify further scientific research. Furthermore, wildfires serve a dual role by maintaining open habitats in the area, preventing the encroachment of scrub vegetation or woodland closure. This helps to preserve the availability of suitable habitats for the species. Consequently, the potential impact of wildfires on the population could range from low/moderate to severe, particularly given the likelihood of an extended fire season and increased severity due to climate change.

Roads: *Xerocrassa setubalensis* was frequently found in open, disturbed ground near roadsides, where access is strongly facilitated. This suggests that the species could potentially colonize rocks in newly exposed areas resulting from road maintenance or widening activities. However, due to its limited ability to disperse over long distances, roads may contribute to

habitat fragmentation and reduce connectivity between sub-populations. Due to several environmental legislative restrictions, there are no substantial plans for significant road development in the area expected in the near future. As a result, the impact of roads on the species is potentially weak to moderately significant.

Climate change: The Mediterranean region is anticipated to experience more frequent droughts in the future (UNEP/MAP & PLAN BLEU, 2020). Land snails, in general, are highly susceptible to desiccation, although xerophilous species such as *X. setubalensis* have evolved mechanisms to endure drought conditions (NICOLAI & ANSART, 2017). They achieve this by restricting most of their activity to periods of high air humidity, primarily during the winter, which typically coincides with their reproductive season. Extended droughts may result in reduced activity and longer aestivation periods (e.g., SCHEIL, KÖHLER & TRIEBSKORN, 2011). This could potentially have adverse consequences, such as difficulties in finding mating partners and feeding (NICOLAI & ANSART, 2017). We have found an almost perfect match with the distribution area the southern faced cliffs (Figure 3) that are expected to be more exposed to drought event and extended periods of higher temperatures. The impact is therefore assessed as moderately significant.

Assessing the conservation status

Criterion A (population reduction) could not be employed in this assessment since this survey marked the first extensive examination of the species. Consequently, we lack data on any population or range size changes. Furthermore, although the species appear to be closely tied to specific habitat types (xerophilous vegetation, rocky cliffs) it is difficult to deduce population changes associated with shifts in the extent of those habitats.

Regarding criterion B (geographic range), three specific conditions must be met concurrently: a small range in conjunction with, either habitat fragmenta-

tion or a reduced number of locations, and a demonstrated pattern of either ongoing decline or extreme population fluctuations.

While the extent of occurrence (EOO) was less than 100 km², there are still no available data to support the existence of extreme population fluctuations. An ongoing decline could only be inferred by noting that the live *X. setubalensis* were found in a narrow strip of habitats within the larger area where shell remains were detected, which suggests a contraction of the living range.

The habitats surveyed are mainly shrubby environments near cliffs, bordering the ocean, where it is difficult to cover large areas in a continuous way. The difficulties of sampling are a limiting factor for us to assess the continuity of distribution of the species, despite the presumed limited dispersal capacity. Quarrying and some urban nuclei as Sesimbra certainly cause habitat fragmentation, but their real consequences to the species' genetic flow is not known. In the eastern nucleus, the type locality of the species near the city of Setúbal, where most of the historical data came from, it was only possible to locate very few empty shells, despite the sampling effort. It is therefore possible that this subpopulation is now extinct.

Regarding the number of locations, following the IUCN definition of a location as "a geographically or ecologically distinct area where a single threatening event can swiftly impact all individuals of the taxon present", and given the usual extent of fires in the region, we consider that two separate locations may exist (eastern, and western), separated by Sesimbra village and a quarry. Nevertheless, given that locations are restricted to a narrow land strip, future wildfires or land use changes (urban sprawl or quarries) can contribute to increase the segregation between the two identified subpopulations (Figure 3) or significantly reduce the extent of live occupancy which was estimated in less than 20 km².

We have no robust data to infer on criterion C (small population size and decline). However, our crude popula-

tion estimates suggest a much larger population than the limit of 10,000 individuals proposed by IUCN.

Criterion E, which involves the quantitative analysis of extinction risk, could not be utilized in this assessment due to the unavailability of essential data necessary for conducting a Population Viability Analysis or any other quantitative analysis.

CONCLUSIONS

Here we present the updated distribution area of *Xeroplexa setubalensis*, a land snail endemic to the Serra da Arrábida and littoral cliffs facing southwards in the Setúbal peninsula, Portugal. Based on specific fieldwork and compiled anecdotic information it is now possible to have a rather accurate distribution map, which differs from that available on the IUCN Red List page (MARTÍNEZ-ORTÍ, 2011), by extending ≈ 20 km the western limits on the Serra da Arrábida. The species is no longer assigned to one single location but we identified two locations spreading along a narrow strip associated with L2-type limestone facing southwards, that can easily be partitioned by a quarry or urban sprawling.

By applying the IUCN criteria, we recommend keeping the same conservation status of “Endangered” as depicted in the previous assessment (MARTÍNEZ-ORTÍ, 2011), although for different reasons (explained above). Hence, the

species meets the following criteria, according to the IUCN (2012): Geographic range in the form of either extent of occurrence (EOO) or area of occupancy (AOO) or both, which is the case. Extent of occurrence estimated to be less than 5,000 km², area of occupancy estimated to be less than 500 km², severely fragmented, with inferred continuing decline (i) EOO, (ii) AOO and (iv) number of locations or subpopulations. In IUCN’s notation: B1ab(i)(ii)(iv) + B2 ab(i)(ii)(iv).

It should be stressed, however, that the species’ entire range falls within a Natura 2000 site (Arrábida-Espichel PTCON0010) and a Natural Park, which could aid in the implementation of management measures and restrictions that are compatible with the conservation of the species.

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